

ANTIBIOSIS STUDY OF *EARIAS VITTELLA* (FABRICIUS) ON SELECTED OKRA GENOTYPES

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted in the laboratory of Entomology Department, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, Dist. Ahmednagar (Maharashtra) during the year summer 2015 to know the biology of *E. vittella* on selected okra genotypes. Fruits of four okra genotypes viz., Narendra (0-5%) infestation as resistant, EC-372 (5.1-15%) as moderately resistant, VRO-12 (15.1-30%) as moderately susceptible and IC-140902 (> 30.1%) as susceptible were used for feeding the larvae of *E. vittella* during studies. Resistant genotype Narendra showed lower (53.75%) survival rate, more (15.46 days) larval periods, lowest (55.63 mg) larval weight, more (46.25%) larval mortality, longest (10.53 days) pupal period, lower (41.16 mg) pupal weight, minimum (84.81%), adult emergence and less (3.26) growth index. In ovipositional preference study, the female moth of *E. vittella* laid less (224.75 eggs female⁻¹) number of eggs on resistant genotype Narendra. The larvae reared on fruits of susceptible genotype IC-140902 registered highest (86.25%) survival rate, minimum (10.10 days) larval period, highest (74.81 mg) larval weight, least larval mortality (13.75%), shorter (5.43 days) pupal period, highest (54.52 mg) pupal weight, maximum (91.65%) adult emergence and more (6.07) growth index. The susceptible genotype IC-140902 recorded maximum 381.16 eggs per female. The data pertaining to biology of *E. vittella* on selected okra genotypes revealed fast development of *E. vittella* was recorded in susceptible genotypes as compared to resistant genotypes primarily due to some biophysical and biochemical parameters.

Key words: okra, *Earias vittella*, shoot and fruit borer, genotype.

Introduction

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L. Moench), belongs to family Malvaceae. It is an important vegetable crop grown in the mediterranean as well as in the tropical and sub tropical region (Yawalkar, 1992) and most popular in India grown throughout the year. Several biotic and abiotic factors are responsible for low yield of okra. Okra plant is attacked by 72 species, during their different growth stages, which are major constraints in getting higher yields (Kumar *et al.*, 2002 and Gulati, 2004). Shoot and fruit borer, *E. vittella* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is causing economic damage to the crop at all the growth stages. The okra cultivators spray frequently chemical insecticides, to kill the larvae before they enter into the shoots or fruits. The indiscriminate use of pesticides creates problem of insecticide resistance, pest resurgence, adversely affect the non target species, environmental pollution and pesticides residues in harvested okra fruits and hazardous to the consumers (Jat and Pareek, 2003).

We consider today's era as an era of IPM where integration of all the control measures is likely to be done, whereas an insect resistant plant offer ideal prevention against insect damage, involved minimum cost of production and are ecofriendly. Thus in vegetable crop there is greatest scope for evolving pest resistant variety.

The morphological and biochemical characters of the cultivars also play an important role in expressing host plant resistance in plants. These characters of different okra cultivars need to be studied thoroughly for the development of resistance to the pest. Therefore, it was felt necessary to study the antibiosis effect of okra cultivar on the development of *E. vittella*.

Materials And Method

The antibiosis study was undertaken in laboratory of Department of Entomology, PGI, MPKV, Rahuri during 2015, the mass rearing of okra shoot and fruit borer was done as per the procedure adopted by Satpute *et al.* (2005) at ambient temperature of 25 to 27°C with 70 to 80 per cent relative humidity.

The collected larvae were reared by providing fresh small pieces of fruits for their feeding. On every alternate day the feed were changed until the pupation. These pupae were collected and transferred to plastic jars for adult emergence. The newly emerged moths were fed with 5 per cent honey based adult diet.

The four genotypes viz. Narendra (Resistant), EC-372 (Moderately resistant), VRO-12 (Moderately susceptible) and IC- 140902 (Susceptible) which were previously screened out in the field

condition against *E. vittella* were used in the experiment. The fruits of these genotypes were used as a feeding material for the larvae of *E. vittella* in laboratory condition.

Twenty freshly hatched larvae were reared individually on each of the genotypes until pupation and were replicated five times.

The effects of fruits of these four genotypes on the biology of *E. vittella* were studied on the basis of different parameters viz. per cent survival of larvae, larval period, larval weight, larval mortality, pupal period, pupal weight, adult emergence, growth index and fecundity.

Results And Discussion

The data pertaining to biology of okra shoot and fruit borer on selected okra genotypes are presented in Table 1. The rearing of *E. vittella* on fruits of different four genotypes (one from each grade i.e. resistant, moderately resistant, moderately resistant and susceptible) was done under laboratory condition.

The effects of fruits of these four genotypes on the biology of *E. vittella* were studied on the basis of following parameters.

Survival of larvae

The data on per cent survival of larvae indicated that the larvae reared on fruits of resistant genotype Narendra showed significantly lower survival (53.75%) and it was statistically superior to rest of the genotypes. The larvae reared on fruits of susceptible genotype IC-140902 registered highest 86.25 per cent survival rate. The moderately resistant genotype recorded 66.25 per cent larval survival followed by moderately susceptible genotype VRO-12 (76.25%).

Larval period

The data recorded on larval period revealed that the differences in larval periods on different genotypes were statistically significant. *E. vittella* reared on fruit of resistant genotype Narendra showed maximum larval period of 15.46 days. Moderately resistant genotype EC-372 recorded 13.03 days of larval periods and it was found at par with moderately susceptible VRO-12 (12.23 days). Significantly minimum larval period was required for larval development in case of susceptible genotype IC-140902 (10.10 days). In general, descending trend of larval period was observed from resistant to susceptible genotypes.

Larval weight

The results on larval weight showed significantly lowest larval weight (55.63 mg) gained in resistant genotype Narendra followed by moderately resistant genotype EC-372 (64.92 mg) whereas moderately susceptible VRO-12 was recorded 69.60 mg larval weight. The influence of susceptible genotype IC-140902 was found

statistically significant recorded 74.81 mg larval weight. There was increasing trend in larval weight from resistant to susceptible genotypes.

Larval mortality

The data recorded on larval mortality revealed that the highly resistant genotype Narendra showed significantly more larval mortality (46.25%) on fruit as against other genotypes. The moderately resistant genotype EC-372 recorded 33.754 per cent larval mortality followed by moderately susceptible genotype VRO-12 (23.75%). However, the larvae reared on fruits of susceptible genotype IC-140902 (13.75%) registered lower as larval mortality. It was concluded that the trend of larval mortality was decreasing from resistant to susceptible genotype.

Pupal period

Pupal period of *E. vittella* was an average extended significantly in the larvae reared on resistant genotype Narendra by recording 10.53 days pupal period following moderately resistant genotypes EC-372 (9.39 days). However, shorter pupal period 5.43 days was noticed in the larvae reared on susceptible genotype IC-140902 and moderately susceptible genotype VRO-12 recorded 7.49 days pupal period. It indicates, that descending trend of pupal period was observed on resistant to susceptible genotype.

Pupal weight

The larvae reared on resistant genotype Narendra recorded lowest weight of pupa (41.16 mg) as compared to susceptible genotype IC-140902 (54.52 mg). Larvae reared on moderately resistant genotype EC-372 recorded 45.35 mg pupal weight. However, moderately susceptible genotype VRO-12 recorded (51.21 mg) pupal weight. It was concluded that pupal weight increased significantly from the larvae reared on resistant genotype to susceptible genotype.

Adult emergence

The data on average adult emergence ranged from 84.81 to 94.11 per cent was found statistically significant. The larvae reared on resistant

genotype recorded minimum (84.81%) adult emergence followed by EC-372 (88.58%). Whereas, larvae reared on moderately susceptible genotype VRO-12 and susceptible genotype IC-140902 recorded 91.65 and 94.11 per cent moth emergence, respectively and were found to be statistically at par with each other. It indicated that the trend of per cent moth emergence was increasing from resistant to susceptible genotypes.

Growth index

The data indicated that larvae of *E. vittella* the pest reared on the susceptible genotype IC-140902 (6.07) recorded a maximum growth index. VRO-12, the moderately susceptible genotype recorded 4.67 followed by moderately resistant genotype EC-372 (3.96) and resistant genotype Narendra (3.26). It was concluded, the growth index was increasing from resistant to susceptible genotype.

Fecundity

The data on average fecundity per female revealed that the *E. vittella* reared on resistant genotype Narendra (224.75 eggs female⁻¹) laid less followed by moderately resistant genotype EC-372 (272.16 eggs female⁻¹) and moderately susceptible genotype VRO-12 (348.35 eggs female⁻¹). The resistant susceptible genotypes IC-140902 recorded 381.16 eggs which was significantly more fecundity per female over others. Increasing rate of egg laying was found from resistant to susceptible genotypes. These findings of antibiosis study are in agreement with Kranz *et al.*, (1977); Ambegaonkar and Bilapate (1982); Hiremath (1984); Bichoo (1989); Vyas and Patel (1990); Mursal (2000); Suryawanshi *et al.*, (2001) and Kumar *et al.*, (2014). In antibiosis study the fast development of *E. vittella* was recorded in susceptible genotypes as compared to resistant genotypes. The resistance might be due to imparting some biophysical and biochemical parameters. On the basis of this biological study it is resulted that the resistant genotypes extended the life cycle of pest and fecundity hence reduced the number of generation per year as well as reproductive capacity of *E. vittella*.

Table 1. Survival and development of *E. vittella* on fruits of different okra genotypes.

Tr. No.	Genotypes and category	Larval Survival (%)	Larval Period (Days)	Larval weight (mg)	Larval mortality (%)	Pupal period (Days)	Pupal weight (mg)	Adult emergence (%)	Growth Index	Fecundity (Nos.)
1	Narendra (Resistant)	53.75 (47.16) *	15.46	55.63	46.25 (42.84)	10.53	41.16	84.81 (67.14)	3.26	224.75
2	EC-372 (Moderately Resistant)	66.25 (54.52)	13.03	64.69	33.75 (35.48)	9.39	45.35	88.58 (70.45)	3.96	272.16
3	VRO-12 (Moderately Susceptible)	76.25 (60.91)	12.23	69.60	23.75 (29.09)	7.49	51.21	91.65 (73.41)	4.67	348.35
4	IC-140902 (Susceptible)	86.25 (68.44)	10.10	74.81	13.75 (21.56)	5.43	54.52	94.11 (75.95)	6.07	381.16
	S.E. (m) ±	1.61	0.43	1.15	1.61	0.33	0.97	1.36	0.17	10.02
	CD at 0.01 %	4.96	1.32	3.55	4.96	1.01	3.00	4.20	0.52	30.88

* Figures in parentheses are arc sine transformed values

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